

Research paper

Dispatch optimization and sizing of molten-salt power-to-heat systems in balancing electricity markets for industrial heat electrification

Pavla Lukášová^{ID}*, Adam Kubín^{ID}, Radek Procházka^{ID}

Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University in Prague, Technická 1902/2, Praha 6, 166 27, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Dataset link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19003263>

Keywords:

Power-to-heat
Thermal energy storage
Industrial decarbonization
Balancing services
Dispatch optimization
Linear programming

ABSTRACT

Decarbonization of industry remains a major barrier in the energy transition, with industrial process heat being a hard-to-abate source of emissions due to reliance on fossil fuels. To address this challenge, electrification of heat via power-to-heat technologies offers a promising pathway. This work investigates a power-to-heat system integrated with molten-salt thermal energy storage for medium-temperature industrial steam generation. A techno-economic assessment is conducted using a mixed-integer linear programming algorithm to optimize system dispatch under dynamic electricity pricing, including both day-ahead and balancing services markets. Multiple system configurations are evaluated to identify optimal sizing based on the levelized cost of heat, and results are benchmarked against conventional steam generation technologies. Results show that participation in balancing markets improves economic performance, significantly reducing the levelized cost of heat compared to day-ahead market operation alone. When ancillary services are included, the proposed system achieves operational cost savings between 0.9–4 M€/y against electric boiler. Despite growing interest in power-to-heat systems with thermal energy storage, existing studies on industrial steam applications remain scarce and typically do not consider multi-market participation. This study addresses this gap by developing an integrated framework for molten-salt-based power-to-heat systems supplying industrial steam, enabling coordinated dispatch in day-ahead and ancillary service markets under realistic electricity cost structures, including network tariffs. The results provide a basis for further research and future industrial deployment of flexible electrification solutions.

1. Introduction

Industrial decarbonization is a key challenge on the path toward climate neutrality. The industrial sector remains heavily reliant on fossil fuels [1], with renewable energy sources contributing only 14 % to its final energy consumption [2]. It is also the largest end-use sector for both energy demand and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, representing 38 % of total global final energy consumption and 47 % of global CO₂ emissions (including not only process emissions, but also emissions from electricity and heat) [1].

The majority of energy consumed in the industrial sector is used for process heat production [2]. Industrial processes require heat at varying temperature levels, commonly classified as low-temperature (below 150 °C), medium-temperature (150–400 °C), high-temperature (400 °C–1000 °C) and very high-temperature (above 1000 °C) [2]. The wide range of industrial processes complicates decarbonization efforts, as no single solution can effectively address all industrial heat demand [3]. Low-temperature heat can be produced by a variety of low-emission technologies, such as heat pumps, but sustainable

pathways for generating medium- and high-temperature heat remain limited [4]. At the same time, these temperature levels account for the majority of industrial heat demand in the EU [5], highlighting the need for alternative solutions.

Electrification of process heat through power-to-heat (P2H) technologies is widely recognized as a key decarbonization pathway [6]. P2H enables the use of low-carbon electricity to generate industrial heat across a wide range of temperature levels [7]. However, its economic performance is strongly affected by electricity price volatility, which can limit competitiveness.

Thermal energy storage (TES) can address this limitation by increasing operational flexibility. By decoupling electricity consumption from heat demand, TES enables flexible thermal energy management, allowing industries to adapt to fluctuating electricity prices while still delivering heat on demand [8]. The resulting hybrid P2H+TES system provides demand-side flexibility through load shifting and enhances grid stability. In addition, it enables participation in ancillary service markets, creating additional revenue streams [9].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: pavla.lukasova@fel.cvut.cz (P. Lukášová).

Nomenclature

η_{EH}	EH efficiency [-]
η_{SGS}	SGS efficiency [-]
$BidSR$	Bid Success rate [-]
Cap_{aFRR}	aFRR reserved capacity [MW _e]
E_{TES}	TES capacity [MWh _{th}]
P_{cap}	Capacity reservation price [€/MWh]
P_{DAM}	DAM electricity price [€/MWh]
P_{dist}	Regulated network fees price [€/MWh]
P_{EH}	EH power [MW _e]
P_{EH}^{aFRR}	EH power in aFRR [MW _e]
P_{EH}^{DAM}	EH power in DAM [MW _e]
P_{loss}	Thermal losses [MW _{th}]
P_{RE}	RE activation price [€/MWh]
Q_{th}	Thermal load [MW _{th}]
r_d	discount factor [-]
RE_{act}	RE Activation ratio [-]
RE_{time}	Fraction of hour BSP is activated [-]
SoC	TES State of Charge [-]
$X(t)$	Binary operation status of EH (1 = ON, 0 = OFF)

Acronyms

aFRR	Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve
AS	Ancillary Services
BoS	Balance of System
BSP	Balancing Service Provider
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CB	Coal-fired boiler
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
DAM	Day-ahead market
DEC	Decommissioning costs
DHN	District Heating Network
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EB	Electric Boiler
EH	Electric Heater
ETS	Emissions Trading System
GAMS	General Algebraic Modeling System
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Heat
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Program
MS	Molten salt
NOB	Net Operational Benefit
NOC	Net Operational Cost
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
OPEX	Operational expenses
P2H	Power-To-Heat
RE	Regulating Energy
REV	Balancing market revenues
RTE	Round Trip Efficiency
SGS	Steam Generation System
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
TSO	Transmission System Operator

TES systems can be designed for specific temperature levels by selecting appropriate storage materials, enabling coverage of a wide range of industrial heat demands. The most mature systems are based

on sensible heat storage. These systems raise, resp. lower, the temperature of the storage material to store, resp. release, heat. Common storage materials include water, thermal oils, molten salts, and solid media such as rocks, concrete, sand, and ceramics. Applications range from low-temperature water tanks to high-temperature molten-salt systems used in concentrated solar power (CSP) plants with GWh-scale capacities [10]. In contrast, latent and thermochemical heat storage technologies remain less mature and require further development [11].

Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of electrification in various industrial sectors, including pulp and paper industry [12], food and beverage industry [13], chemical industry [14], steel industry [15], or glass industry [16]. Bottom-up analysis suggests that up to 78 % of industrial heat demand in Europe can be electrified using mature technologies, with emerging solutions increasing this share to nearly 99 % [7]. TES is increasingly recognized as a key enabling technology for waste heat recovery and improved operational flexibility [17]. Recent review highlights rapid development of medium- and high-temperature TES solutions, with sensible heat storage being the most mature and approaching industrial deployment [11]. Moreover, successful operation of a pilot molten-salt TES unit with an electric heater supplying heat to a district heating network was reported in [18], demonstrating its potential for participation in flexibility markets due to fast activation times.

Despite this progress, most existing studies focus on low-temperature applications, particularly district heating networks (DHNs). These include P2H solutions for absorbing excess renewable generation using heat pumps [19] and electric boilers [20], as well as optimization of TES sizing for wind-powered P2H systems [21]. In contrast, high-temperature industrial applications remain less extensively studied, despite their dominant share in final energy consumption.

Moreover, the limited number of existing techno-economic studies in industrial contexts often rely on simplified assumptions, including limited use of real operational data and market price signals, and frequently neglect key cost components such as network tariffs [22]. More advanced optimization-based studies highlight the importance of time-resolved dispatch for economic performance. In this context, Hamilton et al. demonstrate that mixed-integer linear programming (MILP)-based dispatch can increase revenues from electricity market participation [23], while Trevisan et al. also employ a MILP framework and show that optimized P2H+TES operation reduces costs compared to conventional operation of electric boilers [24].

In addition, participation of P2H+TES systems in ancillary service markets has been investigated only to a limited extent, mainly in district heating applications. An operational strategy for DHNs across multiple energy markets, including balancing markets, was proposed in [25]. The importance of TES and reserve market operation for mitigating electricity price volatility in electrified DHNs was highlighted in [26]. However, no studies focused on industrial heat production have been reported.

In summary, there is a clear research gap in the techno-economic analysis of P2H systems integrated with TES for medium- and high-temperature industrial heat supply, particularly under realistic operational and market conditions, and in their ability to provide balancing services to the grid.

This study addresses this gap by developing a MILP-based dispatch optimization model for a molten salt-based P2H+TES system supplying industrial steam while participating in both day-ahead and ancillary service electricity markets. To the best of our knowledge, no previous work has combined industrial-scale heat supply, TES, and ancillary services provision within a unified optimization framework that also accounts for full electricity cost structures, including network tariffs.

The proposed P2H+TES system is evaluated through a techno-economic analysis, using the developed MILP model for optimal dispatch. Different system configurations are assessed to determine optimal sizing. Finally, The methodology is applied to a real industrial case study and results are compared with conventional steam generation technologies.

Fig. 1. Layout of the proposed TES-integrated P2H system.

2. System description and balancing market framework

This section describes the configuration of the investigated system and provides an overview of the balancing market framework, serving as the basis for the modeling assumptions introduced in the subsequent methodology.

2.1. System configuration

A block diagram of the investigated P2H system integrated with high-temperature TES is shown in Fig. 1. The system comprises three main functional units: P2H system, TES system, and the Steam Generation System (SGS).

The proposed TES system is based on a two-tank configuration, typically used at CSPs, consisting of hot and cold storage tanks and utilizing molten salt (MS) as the heat transfer and storage medium. A key advantage is that both storage tanks operate at near-atmospheric pressure, avoiding the need for expensive pressure-rated vessels [27]. The proposed TES system utilizes Yara MOST (trade name), a ternary salt mixture based on potassium-nitrate (KNO_3), sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) and calcium nitrate (CaNO_3). The operational range of MS is defined by its freezing point and maximum allowable temperature, which is limited by thermal decomposition. The thermophysical properties of YARA MOST are detailed in Appendix, Table A.5. To compensate for heat losses and to prevent salt freezing, the MS system (including tanks, piping or valves) is equipped with auxiliary electric heaters. The circulation of MS is ensured by pumps.

The P2H conversion is performed by a resistance electric heater (EH), that heats the MS during charging. The SGS includes a series of heat exchangers transferring heat between molten salt and water/steam. In the proposed SGS, an economizer followed by an evaporator is considered. However, if superheated steam is required by the customer, a superheater can be added to the system.

The proposed system can operate in multiple modes. In charging mode, the cold MS is pumped from the cold tank through the EH, where it is heated to target temperature, and stored in the hot tank. Multiple EH units can be used to speed up the charging process and take advantage of times with negative electricity prices. During the discharging, hot MS is circulated from the hot tank through the SGS, transferring thermal energy to water to generate steam for industrial processes. The cooled MS returns to the cold tank. The proposed system also enables simultaneous charging & discharging. In this case, part of the MS is heated while another part is discharged, allowing flexible response to electricity price fluctuations or steam demand. Another possible mode of operation is idle mode, where the MS remains stored for later use and does not circulate through the system. Pumps and control valves

regulate MS flow. The dispatch optimization algorithm determines when to charge, discharge, or remain idle based on electricity market prices, thermal demand, and storage state of charge.

2.2. Balancing services market description

Since the proposed P2H system coupled with TES provides sufficient dynamic response and operational flexibility, this study considers not only electricity procurement on the day-ahead market (DAM) but also trading of technical flexibility, i.e., participation in the balancing services market. For demand-side assets such as TES system with an electric heater, the most suitable service is the provision of negative automatic frequency restoration reserve (aFRR-).

2.2.1. Balancing market mechanism

Automatic frequency restoration reserve is a balancing service that helps maintain grid frequency stability. It is automatically activated by the transmission system operator (TSO) in response to frequency deviations. Balancing service providers (BSPs) offering aFRR must ensure that their contracted reserve is fully activated within five minutes. Negative aFRR (aFRR-) represents a downward regulation, where the BSP reduces generation or increases consumption, thereby absorbing power from the grid.

- Capacity Reservation: Capacity for aFRR is procured through daily auctions organized either at the national level or via shared international platforms such as ALPACA. The allocation follows a pay-as-bid principle. Offers are ranked according to the bid price, and the required capacity is selected by an optimization algorithm, with successful bidders receiving their individual bid price. The minimum bid size for participation is 1 MW, with a bidding granularity of 1 MW.
- Balancing Energy Activation: The activation of regulating energy (RE) is coordinated through the international PICASSO platform, which integrates aFRR providers across Europe. The PICASSO algorithm runs at a 4-second resolution, continuously optimizing and dispatching the most cost-efficient resources to restore system balance. Here, a marginal pricing mechanism applies.

2.2.2. Revenue structure

The remuneration structure for aFRR consists of two complementary revenue streams:

- (i) Capacity Revenue (availability payment) – BSPs receive payment for holding reserve capacity available for activation, regardless of whether activation occurs. Capacity remuneration is typically expressed in €/MW.h.

- (ii) Energy Revenue (activation payment) – BSPs are also compensated for the actual RE delivered during reserve activations. This element of remuneration reflects the real-time provision of flexibility to the system. Energy payment is expressed in €/MWh.

It should be noted that when the BSP is activated to provide aFRR-service, energy-dependent network charges apply. Consequently, in this study, all references to energy revenue from the aFRR- market refer to net revenue, defined as the activation payment from TSO the BSP minus the applicable energy-dependent network charges.

2.2.3. Bid price determination

The BSP submits two distinct bid prices - for capacity reservation and for RE activation. Their determination is described below.

- (i) Bid price for capacity reservation – In this paper, the bid price for capacity reservation in a given hour is conservatively calculated as the average price on the capacity reservation market during that hour.
- (ii) Bid price for activation of RE – From an economic perspective, activation of RE is attractive whenever the marginal price in the balancing market falls below the provider's opportunity cost of heat production. The relevant alternative in this case is generating the same amount of heat using electricity purchased on the DAM. In other words, it is economically rational to submit a bid for activation at a level lower than the effective cost of producing the heat through electricity procured on the DAM. An approach based on this principle is used to determine the bid price for activating RE in this paper.

Note that positive values of RE price indicate payments from the BSP to the TSO, whereas negative values correspond to payments from the TSO to the BSP. The RE is activated only when the balancing market marginal price falls below the bid price. For example, a bid price of 10 €/MWh means the BSP will pay up to 10 €/MWh if activated (marginal price lower than 10 €/MWh), while -10 €/MWh means activation only if the TSO pays at least 10 €/MWh (marginal price lower than -10 €/MWh).

3. Methods

The flowchart in Fig. 2 illustrates the methodology applied in this study, summarizing the sequence of methods and emphasizing the key inputs, outputs, and performance metrics. The dispatch optimization algorithm is implemented in General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS) tool and solved with the Cplex 22.1.0.0 solver, with integrality gap of 0.01. The model runs with a one-hour time step over a one-year optimization horizon. The thermal loss model and the economic model were implemented in Python, and all subsequent post-processing calculations were also performed in Python.

First, input data are collected, including technical parameters as well as time-series data such as thermal demand profiles and market prices. A complete description of all input data is provided in Section 3.5. Next, a detailed heat transfer analysis is performed to quantify thermal losses (Section 3.2). Based on the technical specifications of the TES system (e.g., geometry and insulation properties), thermal losses are approximated as a linear function of the TES state of charge and are fed into the dispatch optimization model as input data.

At the core of this study, and its main contribution, is the dispatch optimization algorithm, formulated as a mixed-integer linear program and presented in Section 3.1. The output of the MILP model is optimal operating schedule.

Subsequently, a bottom-up economic model is developed to evaluate the economic performance of the proposed system (Section 3.3). Several techno-economic key performance indicators (KPIs), including the Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH), are defined to assess system performance and compare it against conventional technologies. The

benchmark scenarios and underlying assumptions are described in Section 3.5.7. Following this, optimal system sizing is determined using a discrete optimization approach. As a final step, the impact of key assumptions is assessed through sensitivity analysis.

3.1. Dispatch optimization model

The goal of the studied system is to supply process steam to the industrial customer on demand. Without TES, the P2H system would consume electricity exactly at the same time as heat is demanded. TES integration allows for demand-side management by shifting electricity consumption to low-price periods and storing thermal energy to meet later heat demand. The charging schedule is therefore guided by market conditions, but remains constrained by the heat demand and the technical limits of the TES-integrated P2H system. In addition to participation in the DAM, the system is also studied in the context of flexible electricity markets, where it can provide balancing services to the grid. As a result, the dispatch schedule is further influenced by the requirements and opportunities of these balancing markets.

In this paper, operating schedule is determined by developing an optimization model formulated as MILP. MILP is a widely used method for handling optimization problems that involve both continuous and discrete variables, allowing precise scheduling decisions while respecting system constraints. MILP provides an effective way to achieve optimal operation in complex, dynamic systems such as the studied P2H+TES system, operating on both the DAM and aFRR- market.

In the model equations below, the model timestep $\Delta t = 1$ h is omitted. All power terms are understood to represent energy flows over one-hour intervals, ensuring consistent units for storage dynamics, dispatch calculations, and cost evaluation. This convention applies to SoC update, EH dispatch, reserve activations, and objective function evaluation throughout the model.

3.1.1. Objective function

The objective of the dispatch optimization algorithm is to minimize variable OPEX and maximize aFRR revenues. This is represented in Eq. (1). The first two terms represent the cost of purchasing electricity in DAM and aFRR dispatch, including energy-dependent network charges, while the third term represents the revenue from providing reserve capacity.

$$F = \min \left[\sum_{t=0}^N (p_{\text{DAM}}(t) + p_{\text{dist}}) P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{DAM}}(t) + (p_{\text{RE}}(t) + p_{\text{dist}}) P_{\text{EH}}^{\text{aFRR}}(t) - C a p_{\text{aFRR}}(t) p_{\text{cap}}(t) \right] \quad \forall t \in \tau \quad (1)$$

Variable OPEX is limited to the cost of electricity consumed by the EH. Auxiliary equipment electricity consumption (e.g., MS pumps, water pumps, monitoring system) is insignificant compared to the EH load. Therefore, it is omitted from the objective function but accounted for in the overall economic model. Furthermore, only variable regulated electricity network charges are considered in the optimization process. Parameter p_{dist} is the sum of all energy-dependent regulated network charges. Fixed capacity network charges do not affect the optimization; therefore, they are excluded from the objective function but included in the overall economic model. The values of all regulated electricity network charges are described in Appendix, Table B.6.

3.1.2. System constraints

The State of Charge (SoC) of the TES system is defined by the energy balance in Eq. (2). The SoC increases when the EH is activated and charges the TES system and decreases when the steam generation system extracts thermal energy Q_{th} , while also accounting for heat losses P_{loss} .

Fig. 2. Flowchart illustrating methodology of this paper.

$$SoC(t) = SoC(t - 1) + \frac{[P_{EH}^{DAM}(t) + P_{EH}^{aFRR}(t)] \cdot \eta_{EH} - \frac{Q_{th}(t)}{\eta_{SGS}} - P_{loss}(t - 1)}{E_{TESnom}} \quad \forall t > 0 \quad (2)$$

Heat losses from storage tanks depend on the TES SoC, as higher stored energy (corresponding to a higher hot MS level) results in increased heat dissipation. For implementation in the MILP formulation, the SoC from the previous time step is used, introducing a one-hour delay that is negligible due to the high thermal inertia of the TES system. To integrate losses into the MILP model, they are approximated as a linear function of the TES SoC. The derivation of this linear approximation, including the detailed thermal loss model and input data, is provided in Section 3.2 and Supplementary Material, section S1. A conservative safety factor is applied in the heat loss estimation procedure, which also accounts for auxiliary losses beyond the storage tanks, including piping and other system components.

Next, Eq. (3) constrains the EH power within its allowable operating range, thereby limiting the maximum charging rate of the TES and influencing both peak-shaving capability and system sizing. Eq. (4) defines minimum and maximum SoC limits, ensuring reliable operation while guiding optimal storage sizing.

$$X(t) \cdot P_{EH,min} \leq \frac{P_{EH}^{DAM}(t) + P_{EH}^{aFRR}(t)}{P_{EHnom}} \leq X(t) \cdot P_{EH,max} \quad \forall t \in \tau \quad (3)$$

$$SoC_{min} \leq SoC(t) \leq SoC_{max} \quad \forall t \in \tau \quad (4)$$

3.1.3. Balancing services market constraints

Next, constraints governing balancing services provided by the system are introduced. These also define the link between reserved capacity and the resulting RE activation.

$$P_{EH}^{aFRR}(t) = Cap_{aFRR}(t) \cdot RE_{time}(t) \cdot BidSR(t) \cdot RE_{act} \quad t \in \tau \quad (5)$$

The actual aFRR energy delivered in a given hour, defined in Eq. (5), depends on four quantities: $BidSR$, RE_{act} , RE_{time} and Cap_{aFRR} . $BidSR$ is a binary parameter representing the probabilistic success

rate of securing reserved capacity in the bidding process. Activation ratio, RE_{act} , describes the fraction of reserved capacity activated in the selected hour. RE_{time} denotes the fraction of time within the hour during which the EH is activated, based on historical activation and bid price.

$$Cap_{aFRR}(t) \leq (P_{EHnom} \cdot P_{EH,max} - P_{EH}^{DAM}(t)) \cdot BidSR(t) \quad \forall t \in \tau \quad (6)$$

$$Cap_{aFRR}(t) \cdot \eta_{EH} \leq SoC_{max} \cdot E_{TESnom} - SoC(t - 1) \quad \forall t > 0 \quad (7)$$

The available reserved capacity, $Cap_{aFRR}(t)$, is physically limited by both available EH power and TES system's SoC. Eq. (6) limits the bid aFRR capacity to the unused portion of the EH's power, reflecting the physical constraint that the heater cannot exceed its maximum power rating. Eq. (7) further restricts bid reserved capacity based on the TES energy available, ensuring that the storage can sustain activation over the entire bidding window. This enforces a worst-case constraint, assuming the system must sustain the full bid over the entire time window, in accordance with TSO requirements, even if the $RE_{time}(t)$ based on historical data is shorter. This conservative approach prevents overestimating aFRR market revenues and ensures consistency with standard techno-economic practice.

3.1.4. Determination of balancing market parameters

Fig. 3 illustrates the determination of parameters $RE_{time}(t)$ and $p_{RE}(t)$ for a selected hour t . The parameter $p_{RE}(t)$ represents the average marginal price of RE activation associated with the corresponding bid price, as described in Section 2.2.3. The quantity of activated RE is defined by Eq. (5). The figure shows 4-second averaged RE activation prices from aFRR-reserves, highlighting periods in which BSPs with bid prices of 10 €/MWh and -20 €/MWh are activated and the respective RE price.

As observed, higher bid prices lead to more frequent activation and thus increased heat production by the electric heater in the proposed system. For a bid price of 10 €/MWh, $p_{RE}(t)$ equals -37 €/MWh over the hour and the provider is activated for 85 % of the time, as indicated by $RE_{time}(t)$. For a bid price of -20 €/MWh, $p_{RE}(t)$ is -126 €/MWh, reflecting a higher payment from the TSO to the BSP due to the sign convention, while activation occurs for only 22 % of the hour.

Fig. 3. Example of determining $RE_{time}(t)$ and $p_{RE}(t)$ from 4 s averaged prices of activated RE on the Picasso platform.

3.1.5. Model limitations

As a modeling simplification, market trading rules, including gate closure times, are not considered. The model assumes deterministic inputs for DAM and RE prices, activation volumes, and reserve clearing, which limits the representation of market uncertainty and temporal dynamics. Consequently, risk related to low activation or adverse price conditions cannot be explicitly quantified. This limitation is partially mitigated by using average bid prices for balancing reserves and by enforcing a 90 % annual success rate in reserve auctions through the $BidSR(t)$ coefficient.

In addition, the model uses an hourly resolution, whereas in practice bids may be updated at quarter-hour intervals. Market competition, clearing mechanisms, and strategic behavior of other participants are also not represented, as their actions are treated as exogenous. These simplifications are partly addressed through sensitivity analyses presented later in the paper.

3.2. Thermal loss model

Thermal losses of the molten-salt TES system are incorporated into the MILP model using a simplified representation derived from a detailed heat transfer analysis. Assuming the storage tanks are maintained at their nominal temperature, heat losses depend on the TES SoC, which reflects the MS level.

The underlying heat transfer model considers a vertical cylindrical storage tank with insulation and accounts for heat losses through the tank wall, bottom, and roof. The formulation distinguishes between wet and dry regions of the wall, reflecting how the MS level varies with the SoC. This is a commonly adopted approach, as demonstrated in several studies, including [24,28], and [29]. The complete heat transfer model, including governing equations, heat transfer correlations and input parameters, is provided in the Supplementary Material, section S1.

Total thermal losses from the detailed model are approximated by a linear function for integration into the MILP, as expressed in Eq. (8)

$$P_{loss}(t-1) = [c_0 + c_1 \cdot SoC(t-1)] \frac{E_{TESnom}}{E_{TESref}} \quad \forall t \in \tau \quad (8)$$

The coefficients c_0 and c_1 are obtained via regression over the full SoC operating range, yielding a computationally efficient linear representation of SoC-dependent losses. A modular design is assumed, where storage capacity is scaled by adding identical units in parallel; therefore, losses scale proportionally with system size through the ratio E_{TESnom}/E_{TESref} . Here, E_{TESref} denotes the reference TES capacity (10 MWh_{th}), while E_{TESnom} corresponds to the studied case.

Fig. 4. Thermal losses as a function of TES SoC for base case sizing.

3.2.1. Linear approximation

The results of the thermal loss estimation for the base case sizing (TES capacity of 10 MWh_{th}) are shown in Fig. 4. Markers represent results from the detailed heat transfer model, while dashed lines indicate the corresponding linear approximation. The corresponding linear fit for total TES system thermal losses yields coefficients $c_0 = 33.59$ kW and $c_1 = 4.08$ kW.

The observed variation of heat losses with SoC is relatively weak; however, including this dependency in the MILP formulation enables the model to distinguish between different storage states during idle operation, e.g., between a fully charged hot tank and a cold tank.

3.3. Economic model

A bottom-up economic model is built based on component-level inputs derived from literature and real-world market data. To analyze the economic viability of different scenarios and allow for their comparison, several economic KPIs are defined, including capital expenditure (CAPEX), operational expenses (OPEX), balancing market revenue (REV), net operational costs (NOC), net operational benefit (NOB), and the Net Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH).

The CAPEX input data are described in Table 1. CAPEX include the cost of heat storage medium (molten salts), storage system (tanks, insulation, supporting structure), charging system (EH), SGS (heat exchangers), grid integration (transformer, metering), energy management system and Balance of System (BoS) consisting of valves, pumps and piping. Indirect CAPEX is also considered, covering EPC fee (engineering, installation, commissioning) and project development costs (project management, financing, licensing).

Table 1
CAPEX and decommissioning input data.

Component	Value	Unit
Molten salts	1.1	€/kg [30]
Storage system	14.8	€/kWh _{th} [30]
Balance of System	25	€/kWh _{th} [24]
Steam generation system	120	€/kW _{th} [24]
Charging system	114	€/kW _e [31]
Grid integration	12	€/kW _e [31]
Energy management system	100 000	€ [24]
EPC & Project development	30	% of direct CAPEX [31]
Decommissioning costs	5	% of direct CAPEX [30]

1 EUR ≈ 1 USD is assumed.

OPEX constitute mostly of electricity-related costs, specifically the market and the regulated component. The market electricity costs are determined by the dispatch optimization algorithm. The structure and values of regulated network charges are provided in the [Appendix, Table B.6](#). Additional 1 % of these electricity-related costs is added to account for auxiliary equipment electricity consumption, such as MS pumps, water pumps, and monitoring systems. Furthermore, annual operation and maintenance (O&M) costs and annual replacement costs are considered, corresponding to 2 % and 1 % of the direct CAPEX, respectively.

For scenarios in which the system provides aFRR services, balancing market revenues are generated. The total REV value is estimated using the MILP dispatch optimization model. The structure of aFRR- revenues is described in Section [2.2.2](#).

Next, the net operational cost is defined as OPEX minus the REV obtained from ancillary service provision. Negative NOC values indicate that REV exceed OPEX, resulting in positive operational balance. This convention aligns with the cost-minimization framing used in the dispatch optimization algorithm.

$$NOB_A = OPEX_B - OPEX_A + REV_A \quad (9)$$

Another KPI, referred to as the Net Operational Benefit (NOB), is introduced to compare the performance of the proposed system (scenario A) with alternative technology (scenario B), e.g., an electric boiler, as defined in Eq. (9).

$$LCOH = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{(CAPEX_n + OPEX_n - REV_n + DEC_n)}{(1+r_d)^n}}{\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{Q_n}{(1+r_d)^n}} \quad (10)$$

Finally, to assess the cost-effectiveness of the proposed heat generation system over its lifetime, levelized cost of heat is calculated. This metrics determines the average cost of supplied unit of heat while considering all associated expenses over the system's entire lifetime, such as CAPEX, OPEX or decommissioning costs. In case of providing ancillary services, the proposed system can also generate revenue which is subtracted from the expenses in the LCOH formula given in Eq. (10). If these revenues exceed the total lifetime costs, the resulting net LCOH may become negative, indicating that the system yields a net economic profit. In such cases, negative LCOH values should be interpreted as a sign of economic benefit rather than implying that heat is produced at a negative price.

The LCOH is estimated using annual values, assuming that all OPEX, REV and heat demand follow the same yearly profile throughout the system's lifetime N . CAPEX is assumed to occur in year 0, while decommissioning is scheduled in year $N+1$. A 30-year operational period is considered in line with [\[30\]](#). A discount rate r_d of 7 % is applied.

3.4. Optimal sizing selection

Optimal sizing is determined via a discrete optimization approach, where a finite set of candidate configurations is evaluated and the one with the lowest LCOH is selected. The sizing variables include

Table 2
Studied sizing configurations of the system.

EH power [MW]	TES capacity [MWh]			
	10	20	40	80
5	x	x	x	
10	x	x	x	x
20		x	x	x

Table 3
Parameters of the system (base case scenario).

Parameter	Value	Unit
TES capacity	10	MWh _{th}
MS mass	85	t
Tank dimensions (diameter; height)	3 ; 6.5	m ; m
Hot tank operational temperature	480	°C
Cold tank operational temperature	180	°C
TES SoC operational range	0–1	[-]
EH nominal power	5	MW _e
EH (charging) efficiency	0.95	[-]
EH operational range	0.1–1	[-]
Steam delivery temperature	220	°C
Maximum thermal load	3	MW _{th}
SGS (discharging) efficiency	0.97	[-]

the EH nominal power and TES capacity, which are independent. A modular system architecture is considered. To limit computational effort, only a subset of configurations was analyzed; these studied cases are highlighted in [Table 2](#).

3.5. Input data and case study

A comprehensive description of the input datasets employed for the analysis is provided in this section. The developed methodology is employed to assess the performance of the proposed system through a case study of a real plastic manufacturing plant in the Czech Republic. The industrial facility produces plastic compounds and requires saturated steam at 220 °C (2.3 MPa).

3.5.1. Case study parameters

The key technical and sizing parameters for the base case scenario are presented in [Table 3](#). The base-case configuration assumes 5 MW_e of EH power and 10 MWh_{th} of TES capacity. The molten salt inventory already accounts for the minimum required mass to ensure proper MS pump operation, resulting in a TES SOC range from 0 % to 100 %. The operating temperatures of the hot and cold tanks are determined by the thermophysical properties of the molten salt and the boundary conditions imposed by the required steam properties. The efficiencies of the EH and SGS are based on conservative literature values and are consistent with experimental results reported in [\[18\]](#).

3.5.2. Thermal load profile

The thermal load profile is based on the typical operating characteristics of the selected plastic compound manufacturing facility. Although hourly data are confidential, the demand is characterized as approximately constant with minor interruptions due to maintenance. A representative profile is therefore assumed with a constant load of 3 MW_{th} and two planned two-week shutdowns per year.

For the MILP model, the load is pre-processed to include transient start-up demand after shutdowns. A 20-minute warm-up period is represented by an additional load equal to one-third of the hourly demand. It is further assumed that the load includes feedwater preheating to 150 °C to prevent molten salt freezing in the economizer.

Fig. 5. Day-ahead electricity market prices in 2024 for CZ and DE zone.

3.5.3. Electricity market prices

Two DAM zones are investigated, namely the Czech (CZ) and the German-Luxembourg (DE) zone. Electricity DAM prices from 2024, gathered from [32] for CZ and [33] for DE zone, are considered.

The DAM prices throughout year 2024 are depicted in Fig. 5. Despite the interconnection of the transmission grids, price differences between the CZ and DE markets arise during certain hours due to limited cross-border transmission capacity, particularly during periods of high renewable energy generation in Germany. Main statistical information about CZ and DE markets are included in Fig. 5. In 2024, the CZ market exhibited a higher average electricity price, while the DE market was characterized by greater price volatility and a significantly higher number of hours with zero or negative prices. As the share of intermittent renewable energy sources in the energy mix continues to grow, the CZ DAM market is expected to increasingly reflect the price dynamics observed in the DE market, making the DE market a useful reference for the future development of the CZ market.

3.5.4. Balancing market prices

The analysis is based on 2024 data from both the CZ and DE balancing markets. Capacity revenues are estimated from reserve capacity price data. In the Czech market, prices correspond to hourly average accepted bids from the national market [34], while in Germany they are based on four-hour block averages published on the ALPACA platform [35].

Fig. 6 illustrates the variation in aFRR- capacity prices for a selected day in May 2024. Whereas CZ aFRR- prices are relatively stable throughout the day, DE aFRR- prices exhibit significant intraday variability. In 2024, the average aFRR- capacity price in CZ amounted to 10.1 €/MWh with a standard deviation of 18.4 €/MWh. In DE, the

corresponding annual average was 14.5 €/MWh with a standard deviation of 20.6 €/MWh, indicating both higher average remuneration and greater price volatility in the DE zone.

Next, energy revenues are evaluated based on 4-second averaged prices of activated RE obtained from the Picasso platform [34]. For balancing energy, marginal prices can vary between +15 000 and -15 000 €/MWh. Figs. 7 and 8 present heat maps of marginal RE prices on the PICASSO platform for 2024, covering the Czech bidding zone and the German control area of 50Hertz. The heat maps indicate that aFRR-prices are predominantly concentrated (approximately two-thirds of the time) within the range of 25–100 €/MWh. The annual average value of 20.66 €/MWh in the Czech market and 39.75 €/MWh in the German market reflect an overall trend of settlements in which the BSP compensates the TSO.

3.5.5. Balancing market participation parameters

The balancing market participation parameters, namely $BidSR(t)$ and RE_{act} , are defined for the base case analysis. The bid success rate, is assumed to be 0.9. Thus, a binary time series (hourly resolution) is generated, where 90 % of the values (randomly distributed) are equal to one and the remaining values are zero, representing bid acceptance and rejection, respectively.

Next, a decreasing trend of the activation ratio RE_{act} is assumed. This reflects a conservative assumption that higher bid volumes might not get fully utilized. The assumed relationship between RE_{act} and the offered capacity in the aFRR market is illustrated in Fig. 9, detailed parametrization of this function is included in Supplementary Material (Section S2).

Both parameters are chosen based on engineering judgment and practical aFRR market behavior. As they are not derived from specific data, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to assess their impact.

3.5.6. Grid emission factor

Hourly grid carbon intensity data for the year 2024 were obtained from [36,37] for the CZ grid and from [38] for DE grid. The reported electricity emission factor reflects domestic power generation only and does not account for cross-border electricity imports or exports.

The distribution of grid emission factors is shown in Fig. 10. The figure indicates that the average annual grid emission factor in DE grid (0.39 tCO₂eq/MWh) is lower than in CZ grid (0.48 tCO₂eq/MWh). It also shows that the emission factors in the DE zone are more evenly distributed across the full minimum–maximum range, whereas the CZ emission factors are concentrated predominantly at values higher than 0.4 tCO₂eq/MWh.

3.5.7. Scenarios description and interpretation

Several scenarios are defined to evaluate system performance under different operational and market conditions, including DAM-only operation (DAM scenario) and combined participation in DAM and ancillary services market (DAM+AS scenario). These are analyzed in two countries, CZ and DE.

Fig. 6. Comparison of balancing reserve prices on CZ and DE aFRR- market for chosen day in 2024.

Service	aFRR-	Price intervals [EUR/MWh]																									
		Payment from BSP to the TSO												Payment from the TSO to the BSP													
Year	Month	>=300	(250, 300]	(200, 250]	(150, 200]	(125, 150]	(100, 125]	(75, 100]	(50, 75]	(25, 50]	(0, 25]	(-50, 0]	(-100, -50]	(-200, -100]	(-300, -200]	(-1000, -300]	(-2000, -1000]	(-3000, -2000]	(-4000, -3000]	(-5000, -4000]	(-6000, -5000]	(-7000, -6000]	(-8000, -7000]	(-9000, -8000]	(-10000, -9000]	>-10000	
2024	January	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.2%	36.8%	23.0%	8.9%	13.0%	11.8%	1.8%	1.6%	0.1%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	February	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	17.6%	36.3%	16.8%	15.8%	10.6%	0.9%	1.3%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	March	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	7.7%	41.1%	17.5%	12.9%	13.7%	2.1%	3.7%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%
	April	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.7%	15.6%	31.4%	9.3%	12.9%	19.3%	5.2%	4.7%	0.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%
	May	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.8%	2.5%	35.1%	18.0%	11.2%	20.1%	3.5%	5.5%	0.8%	0.8%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%
	June	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.7%	1.4%	4.0%	32.3%	26.6%	11.6%	16.1%	3.1%	2.9%	0.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%
	July	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.8%	4.2%	41.9%	22.7%	10.6%	12.0%	2.3%	4.2%	0.3%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%
	August	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	1.3%	3.6%	27.2%	19.6%	13.2%	9.5%	15.5%	2.6%	5.2%	0.8%	0.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.1%
	September	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.9%	2.2%	15.0%	29.7%	14.4%	13.6%	15.3%	4.3%	4.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	October	0.0%	0.5%	0.2%	0.2%	1.2%	1.9%	18.7%	30.4%	20.0%	9.1%	13.7%	1.8%	1.5%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	November	1.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.9%	2.6%	33.3%	28.4%	16.0%	9.1%	7.5%	0.3%	0.3%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	December	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.1%	1.0%	4.1%	29.2%	21.8%	17.7%	11.1%	13.0%	0.7%	0.6%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%

Fig. 7. CZ aFRR- RE prices distribution.

Service	aFRR-	Price intervals [EUR/MWh]																									
		Payment from BSP to the TSO												Payment from the TSO to the BSP													
Year	Month	>=300	(250, 300]	(200, 250]	(150, 200]	(125, 150]	(100, 125]	(75, 100]	(50, 75]	(25, 50]	(0, 25]	(-50, 0]	(-100, -50]	(-200, -100]	(-300, -200]	(-1000, -300]	(-2000, -1000]	(-3000, -2000]	(-4000, -3000]	(-5000, -4000]	(-6000, -5000]	(-7000, -6000]	(-8000, -7000]	(-9000, -8000]	(-10000, -9000]	>-10000	
2024	January	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	4.4%	30.9%	24.8%	11.4%	11.9%	11.3%	3.2%	2.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	February	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	12.0%	34.7%	21.9%	15.9%	10.1%	2.8%	2.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	March	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.3%	1.2%	9.5%	33.3%	24.5%	10.6%	7.4%	4.2%	7.8%	0.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	April	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	1.4%	12.0%	28.2%	13.1%	9.8%	15.4%	8.2%	10.0%	1.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	May	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.3%	0.6%	1.8%	6.7%	29.4%	16.2%	9.5%	18.5%	6.8%	7.6%	1.6%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	June	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	1.0%	2.7%	6.3%	29.8%	22.5%	11.5%	15.0%	3.4%	6.0%	1.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	July	0.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%	0.9%	2.0%	7.2%	31.4%	23.3%	11.0%	11.0%	4.0%	8.0%	0.4%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	August	0.6%	0.0%	0.1%	0.4%	1.9%	3.6%	22.3%	19.5%	15.5%	9.6%	10.8%	4.6%	9.1%	2.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	September	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	1.2%	1.9%	4.9%	17.9%	22.5%	16.1%	10.3%	9.9%	5.9%	8.6%	0.5%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	October	0.6%	0.6%	0.2%	0.4%	1.6%	3.2%	22.2%	27.0%	19.0%	7.5%	10.1%	2.9%	4.6%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	November	1.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.8%	2.7%	35.9%	28.1%	17.1%	5.6%	4.9%	1.6%	1.7%	0.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
	December	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%	0.4%	1.4%	5.3%	29.1%	20.2%	17.4%	9.3%	9.2%	2.4%	4.2%	0.2%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Fig. 8. DE aFRR- RE prices distribution.

Fig. 9. RE_{act} value for provided reserved capacity at aFRR market.

Fig. 10. Distribution of grid emission factors in 2024 in CZ and DE zone.

The DE case combines multiple regional datasets: DAM prices refer to the German–Luxembourg zone, balancing prices to the 50Hertz (TSO) control area, and network tariffs to the E.DIS Netz distribution grid area. The 50Hertz transmission region and the E.DIS distribution area largely overlap in northeastern Germany; therefore, this case represents a regional rather than nationwide configuration. In contrast,

the Czech case is broadly representative at the national level, with a single TSO and network tariffs based on the largest DSO.

The performance of the proposed system is benchmarked against conventional industrial heat generation technologies, an electric boiler (EB scenario) and a coal-fired boiler (CB scenario). A natural gas boiler

Table 4
Techno-economic KPIs for DAM and DAM+AS scenarios (CZ).

Parameter	DAM	DAM+AS	Unit
TES capacity		10	MWh _{th}
EH nominal power		5	MW _e
Thermal load		24.34	GWh _{th} /y
Electricity consumption		26.73	GWh _e /y
Electricity from DAM	100	66	%
Electricity from aFRR-	0	34	%
TES thermal loss	0.31	0.31	GWh _{th} /y
RTE	91	91	%
Total CAPEX		2.37	M€
Total OPEX	2.99	2.05	M€/y
Capacity Revenue	0	0.23	M€/y
Net Energy Revenue	0	0.16	M€/y
Net operational costs	2.99	1.65	M€/y
LCOH	131.04	75.79	€/MWh

is excluded, as coal-based generation dominates the CZ industrial heat sector, which forms the relevant decarbonization baseline. The EB is sized at 5 MW_e to fully meet heat demand.

No thermal buffering is included in the benchmark scenarios, as steam accumulators are generally limited to short-term transient operation rather than energy shifting [39], and their large-scale implementation is economically constrained by pressure vessel costs [27]. EB operates under CZ or DE DAM conditions, while CB represents a lignite-fired unit with identical assumptions in both countries. All parameters are summarized in Table C.7.

4. Results

For each scenario (DAM and DAM+AS), optimal system operation over a representative time window is presented based on the dispatch results. The corresponding techno-economic indicators are then reported, including a comparison between the CZ and DE markets. Sensitivity analyses are conducted for key balancing-market parameters. Finally, the proposed P2H+TES system is benchmarked against conventional steam generation technologies, namely an electric boiler (EB) and a coal-fired boiler (CB).

4.1. Scenario results: day-ahead market

Fig. 11 shows the operation of the proposed system on the DAM, as determined by the developed dispatch optimization algorithm, for three representative days. The demand-side flexibility is effectively utilized, as the operation takes advantage of the full SoC range of the TES system. Two daily price spikes are observed in the analyzed period, during which charging is avoided. The EH power profile thus corresponds to low-price periods, indicating cost-optimal dispatch behavior. Over the selected time window, the maximum DAM price is 120 €/MWh, whereas the highest price at which the system operates in charging mode is 105 €/MWh.

The techno-economic KPIs for the base case sizing are summarized in Table 4. The total P2H round-trip efficiency (RTE), accounting for conversion losses in the P2H system and SGS as well as thermal losses from the TES tanks, is 91 %. Fig. 12 presents the breakdown of both CAPEX and annual OPEX components. SGS, charging system, and indirect costs constitute the largest shares of CAPEX, while electricity-related costs dominate the total OPEX, with wholesale electricity costs accounting for 63 %. Regulated network charges also contribute significantly to the overall OPEX.

Sizing of the P2H+TES system significantly influences the OPEX. Fig. 13 shows that increasing EH power reduces energy-dependent OPEX, as higher power facilitates shifting charging into lower-price hours. A similar decreasing trend is observed when increasing TES capacity, since additional storage allows more high-price hours to be bypassed. However, this reduction continues only up to a certain

Fig. 11. Operation for three chosen days in May 2024. (DAM Scenario, CZ, base case sizing).

Fig. 12. CAPEX and annual OPEX structure (DAM Scenario, CZ, base case sizing).

point. As shown in the 5 MW_e case, increasing TES capacity from 10 MWh_{th} to 20 MWh_{th} reduces OPEX, while a further increase to 40 MWh_{th} leads to a slight increase. At 20 MWh_{th}, the system has already exploited most of its flexibility potential and further capacity addition does not lead to additional OPEX reduction. The same trend can be observed in the 10 MW_e case. In both examples, the storage duration (capacity-to-power ratio of the TES system) of 4 h yields the lowest energy-dependent OPEX.

When full OPEX is considered (Fig. 14), which differs from values presented in Fig. 13 primarily by including the capacity network fee (charged per MW of installed EH power), the trend observable in

Fig. 13. DAM scenario: Energy-dependent OPEX (DAM costs + energy-dependent network charges).

Fig. 14. DAM scenario: Total OPEX.

Fig. 13 reverses, making the scenarios with the lowest EH power the most economically effective in terms of OPEX. As a result, similar pattern can be observed for the LCOH results depicted in Fig. 15. The heatmaps show that, for a given EH power, the optimal storage duration is 2–4 h, in both CZ and DE market. The optimal sizing configuration for both markets yields EH nominal power of 5 MW_e and TES capacity of 10 MWh_{th}.

Comparing the techno-economic KPIs in CZ and DE markets, the lower-priced and more volatile DE market results in lower energy-dependent OPEX. However, once the capacity-based network fee is included, the total OPEX becomes lower in the CZ market. The LCOH values for the 5 MW_e cases are comparable in both markets, but increase at higher installed EH power in DE zone, primarily due to the impact of the capacity network fee.

4.2. Scenario results: day-ahead market with ancillary services

This subsection presents the techno-economic results for the DAM+AS scenario. Fig. 16 illustrates the system operation over three representative days. In the selected period, 73 % of the electricity is procured via the DAM and 27 % via activated RE in the aFRR- balancing market. For example, on 15 May, charging is concentrated in hours with near-zero DAM prices between 0:00 and 2:00, while hours with high RE prices at 6:00 and 19:00 are avoided.

The techno-economic KPIs for the DAM+AS base case are summarized in Table 4. The data shows that the provision of ancillary services not only generates revenues, it also lowers the OPEX, because less electricity needs to be purchased on the DAM. For the base case sizing, the LCOH is reduced by 42 % compared to the DAM-only scenario.

Fig. 17 presents the share between electricity procured at DAM and activated RE for aFRR-. The amount of activated RE increases strongly with higher installed EH power, while TES capacity has only a small effect. For configurations with the largest TES capacities, the share of activated RE decreases slightly compared to intermediate TES capacities.

The composition of OPEX, aFRR market revenues, and the resulting NOC are presented in Fig. 18. DAM energy costs and energy-dependent network charges decrease with increasing EH power, whereas capacity-based network fees increase. As a result, total OPEX decreases when EH power rises from 5 MW_e to 10 MW_e, but increases again at 20 MW_e. For TES, total OPEX decreases up to an intermediate TES capacity, beyond which it increases due to higher thermal losses and higher CAPEX-related OPEX (O&M and replacement costs). In the CZ market, total aFRR- revenues increase with both EH power and TES capacity. In the DE market, energy revenues are negative, while capacity revenues remain positive, resulting in positive total aFRR- revenues. In Fig. 18, costs are plotted as positive values and revenues as negative values, consistent with the cost-minimization formulation of the optimization. For all sizing configurations, NOC is lower in CZ than in DE.

Fig. 19 presents the LCOH for the DAM+AS scenario and all sizing configurations. In contrast to the DAM-only case, where the smallest EH power and TES capacity are generally preferred, larger configurations become more attractive once ancillary services are included. The minimal LCOH is obtained for 20 MW_e and 40 MWh_{th} in CZ market, and for 20 MW_e and 80 MWh_{th} in the DE market. For a given EH power, storage durations of approximately 2–4 h yield the lowest LCOH in both markets, consistent with the DAM-only analysis. In the CZ market, several configurations achieve negative LCOH values, indicating that cumulative revenues from ancillary services exceed the total discounted lifetime costs of the system. In this context, negative LCOH indicates a net economic benefit rather than a negative price for heat.

Overall, for all investigated sizing options, participation in the aFRR- market improves the economic performance compared to the DAM-only scenario, with the largest relative LCOH reductions observed in the CZ market.

4.3. Sensitivity analysis

The sensitivity analysis focuses on two balancing-market parameters with comparatively higher uncertainty: the bid success rate $BidSR(t)$ and the activation ratio RE_{act} . Unlike most balancing market time series, which are derived directly from historical data, these parameters are based on assumptions. The analysis is conducted for the DAM+AS scenario in the CZ market using a system sized at 20 MW_e and 40 MWh_{th}. This configuration is selected because it exhibits low LCOH and is sufficiently large to reflect the impact of changes in balancing-market conditions.

Fig. 20 presents results based on bid success rate. A reduction of BidSR by approximately half leads to a nearly proportional decrease in aFRR market revenues, which consequently increases the LCOH. Changes in activation ratio, shown in Fig. 21, have a smaller impact on LCOH than changes in bid success rate, as capacity revenues represent the dominant share of total aFRR- revenues. Thus, even though a lower activation ratio of RE reduces energy revenues, total revenues are only moderately affected.

Even under substantial deviations of $BidSR(t)$ and RE_{act} from the assumed values, participation in the balancing market consistently improves system performance. Compared to the DAM-only scenario, which yields an LCOH of 163 €/MWh (for the same sizing), the DAM+AS scenario achieves significant improvements, with reductions exceeding 60 % even under worst-case sensitivity conditions presented.

4.4. Comparison with conventional technologies

In this section, the proposed P2H+TES system is benchmarked against a conventional industrial steam generation technologies, namely an electric boiler (EB) and a coal-fired boiler (CB). The comparison is based on the net operational benefit (NOB) and annual CO₂ emissions difference, expressed relative to the emissions of the EB or CB case.

Fig. 15. DAM scenario: LCOH for different sizing configurations. Note: Axes show discrete sizing combinations with uniform spacing for visualization; numerical values are indicated on the tick labels.

Fig. 16. Operation on the DAM and aFRR- market for chosen 3 days in May 2024. (DAM+AS Scenario, CZ, base case sizing).

Fig. 17. DAM+AS scenario: Share of electricity procured via DAM vs. activated RE for aFRR-.

Fig. 18. DAM+AS scenario: NOC, OPEX and Revenues for different sizing.

Fig. 19. DAM+AS scenario: LCOH for different sizing configurations.

Fig. 20. Impact of bid success rate on aFRR revenues and LCOH (DAM+AS, CZ, 20 MW_e & 40 MWh_{th} system).

Fig. 21. Impact of activation ratio on aFRR revenues and LCOH (DAM+AS, CZ, 20 MW_e & 40 MWh_{th} system).

Comparing EB and DAM scenario, where neither of the systems generates revenue from participation in balancing markets, the NOB can be interpreted as electricity cost savings. When only energy-dependent OPEX components are considered (DAM costs and energy-dependent network charges), Fig. 22 shows that the P2H+TES system achieves increasing electricity cost savings with both higher EH power and larger TES capacity. However, when the full OPEX is considered (see Fig. 23), which mainly includes the addition of the capacity-based network fee, the trend changes. Configurations with higher EH power incur higher capacity-based network charges than the EB with 5 MW_e installed power. Consequently, high-power configurations exhibit higher total OPEX than the EB, resulting in negative NOB. For a given EH power, the

largest NOB is obtained for storage durations around 2–4 h, consistent with the LCOH minima observed previously.

Next, the DAM+AS scenario is benchmarked against the EB scenario. Fig. 24 shows that participation in balancing markets significantly increases NOB relative to the EB solution, as it lowers electricity purchases at DAM and generates additional revenues.

Economic benchmarking against CB scenario is presented in Fig. 25. Currently, small heat sources (below 20 MW_{th}) are outside the EU Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), but ongoing policy developments are expected to extend carbon pricing to these sectors [40]. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis of NOB to CO₂ price is performed. Under current conditions, low coal prices limit profitability, and only

Fig. 22. DAM vs. EB scenario: Electricity cost savings (energy-dependent fees only).

Fig. 23. DAM vs. EB scenario: Total OPEX savings.

Fig. 24. DAM+AS vs. EB scenario: NOB.

Fig. 25. DAM+AS (sizing: 20 MW_e and 40 MWh_{th}) vs. CB scenario: NOB for varying carbon price.

the DAM+AS scenario in CZ zone achieves positive NOB relative to CB. Higher CO₂ prices improve the business case, particularly for DAM+AS, but are insufficient to make DAM-only scenarios profitable.

Fig. 26 compares CO₂ emission differences in the CZ and DE markets against EB and CB benchmarks. In the more decarbonized DE grid, both scenarios deliver substantial savings relative to CB, while in the less decarbonized CZ grid DAM achieves only about 5.5 % savings and DAM+AS results in roughly 0.9 % higher emissions. Compared to EB, the DE grid yields net savings under DAM, whereas DAM+AS scenarios increase emissions in both CZ and DE, reflecting a misalignment between low aFRR prices and periods of low grid emission intensity.

5. Discussion

Across several results (see Figs. 13, 17), increasing TES capacity beyond a certain point slightly raises OPEX due to diminishing returns of storage once operational flexibility is saturated. Beyond this point, additional capacity mainly increase thermal losses, which must be compensated by extra electricity consumption. This behavior is specific to the modular configuration assumed in this study, where increasing capacity requires additional storage tanks and thus proportionally higher losses. A single large tank would reduce relative losses and mitigate this behavior.

In the DAM+AS scenario, the share of electricity procured via activated aFRR- increases strongly with EH power but is only weakly dependent on TES capacity for a given EH rating (Fig. 17). This indicates that the TES is frequently discharged and recharged, maintaining sufficient headroom for aFRR- activation, so that the main limiting factor for ancillary service provision is EH power rather than TES capacity. This result can, however, be attributed to the continuous heat load assumed in the case study and cannot be generalized without analyzing different heat load profiles.

The comparison between CZ and DE highlights the role of market and tariff structures in P2H+TES feasibility. In the DAM-only case, lower prices and higher volatility in DE improve arbitrage potential and reduce energy-dependent OPEX, but higher capacity-based network fees offset this advantage, resulting in lower total OPEX and LCOH in CZ zone. In the DAM+AS scenario, CZ benefits further from aFRR-market revenues, while the higher annual average activated RE price (BSP-to-TSO payments) reduces net revenues in DE zone. Overall, both cases show that network tariffs and ancillary services market prices significantly affect system economics.

Regarding emission performance, the results should be interpreted within the specific context of the Czech energy sector, where both electricity and heat generation remain strongly coal-dependent. In this study, we selected a coal-fired boiler as the reference case, as it represents the most relevant baseline. While natural gas boilers are often considered in comparative assessments, they still represent a fossil-based intermediate solution.

In the short term, current carbon intensity of the electricity mix may limit CO₂ emission reductions compared to EB. The higher efficiency of EB relative to the P2H+TES system also contributes to this effect. However, the more decarbonized DE grid already shows the potential for higher reductions with further decarbonization. In the DAM+AS scenario, the current misalignment between economically optimal dispatch and low-carbon periods stems from the fact that ancillary services prioritize grid stability and are remunerated based on availability and systemic need, which currently lacks a direct correlation with real-time carbon intensity.

Nevertheless, electrification remains forward-looking and future-proof strategy. As the power sector decarbonizes, P2H+TES can achieve near-zero operational emissions. In this sense, the proposed system can be viewed as a dual-purpose asset: it supports early deployment by improving economics under current market conditions, and it establishes the technical infrastructure required for a carbon-neutral industrial heat supply in a future low-carbon power system.

Fig. 26. CO₂ emissions difference between the P2H+TES system (sizing: 20 MW_e and 40 MWh_{th}) and the EB and CB benchmark scenarios.

6. Conclusions

This paper presents a comprehensive techno-economic assessment of a P2H+TES system for industrial steam production, with a novel MILP-based dispatch algorithm that simultaneously optimizes participation in both the DAM and the aFRR- market. Two zones, CZ and DE, were analyzed to assess the impact of different market characteristics. Several system configurations are evaluated to identify optimal sizing based on LCOH, and results are benchmarked against conventional steam generation technologies. The DE results should be interpreted as a northeastern Germany case study reflecting the assumed electricity price and tariff settings, rather than representative of the entire German system. The main findings are summarized as follows.

Compared to the optimally sized DAM-only scenario with LCOH of 131 €/MWh, combined participation in the DAM and aFRR- market reduces LCOH to 42 €/MWh in DE and to -12 €/MWh in CZ zone, demonstrating that ancillary service provision substantially improves the economic performance of P2H+TES systems.

Apart from the obvious cost driver, which is the DAM price, network tariffs significantly affect system economics and can change the optimal configuration, shifting the preferred system size. Similarly, balancing market prices also have a clear influence on the business case of the system.

When benchmarked against a conventional non-flexible electric boiler, the proposed P2H+TES configuration achieves operational cost reductions of up to 0.3 M€/y in the DAM-only case and between 0.9–4 M€/y under DAM+AS operation, highlighting the value of demand-side flexibility provided by TES.

Emission performance is highly context-dependent: relative to a coal-fired boiler, P2H+TES reduces CO₂ emissions in CZ DAM and in both DE scenarios. Compared to an electric boiler, emissions are higher in CZ zone and only lower in the DE DAM case. DAM+AS operation tends to increase emissions, reflecting a current misalignment between economically optimal aFRR- dispatch and low-carbon periods. The DE case also serves as an indicative future CZ scenario, suggesting that a more decarbonized grid could enable substantially higher emission reductions.

Overall, this study demonstrates that P2H+TES systems participating in balancing markets can provide cost-competitive and flexible industrial heat, with benefits including improved business cases, enhanced grid stability, and contributions to industrial decarbonization. Given the limited literature on P2H+TES integration in balancing markets, this work provides an initial step toward understanding their techno-economic potential and supports the development and deployment of industrial electrification solutions. Future research could focus on co-optimizing economic and emission objectives in system dispatch, extending the analysis to additional ancillary services, and exploring different industrial processes with varying temperature levels and heat demand profiles, potentially requiring alternative TES configurations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Pavla Lukášová: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Adam Kubín:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Radek Procházka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve language clarity, readability, and overall expression. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This publication was supported by the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

Appendix A. YARA MOST thermophysical properties

Thermophysical properties of the molten salt considered as storage material in the proposed TES system.

Table A.5
YARA MOST thermophysical properties [41].

Parameter	Unit	Value
Composition	[wt %]	KNO ₃ - NaNO ₃ - CaNO ₃ [43 - 15 - 42]
Freezing temperature	[°C]	131
Max. operating temperature	[°C]	500
Specific heat (@ 300 °C)	[J/kg K]	1530
Density (@ 300 °C)	[kg/m ³]	1986
Thermal conductivity	[W/m K]	0.55

Table B.6

Regulated electricity network charges in CZ and DE markets.

Component	Unit	CZ	DE
Capacity-based network charge	€/MW/month	4382	7633
Energy-dependent network charges			
Transmission network tariff	€/MWh	1.8	13.2
System services charge	€/MWh	6.8	^a
Electricity surcharges	€/MWh	19.8	13.3

1 EUR ≈ 25 CZK is assumed.

^a Included in the variable network charge.**Table C.7**

EB and CB parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Value	Source
EB efficiency	[%]	98	[44]
CB efficiency	[%]	75	[45]
Coal emission factor	[tCO ₂ eq/MWh]	0.4	[46]
Coal price	[€/MWh]	5	[47]

Appendix B. Electricity network tariff charges

The electricity network charges considered in this study for CZ [42] and DE [43] markets are summarized in Table B.6. The DE network charges are based on E.DIS Netz, a DSO active in northeastern Germany. The CZ tariffs correspond to the largest distribution area operated by ČEZ. The presented regulated charges apply to industrial consumers connected at the extra-high voltage level.

Appendix C. Benchmarking assumptions

Parameters assumed in the techno-economic benchmarking against conventional technologies, electric boiler (EB) and coal-fired boiler (CB), are summarized below.

Appendix D. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2026.121706>.

Data availability

The data associated with this article are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19003263>.

References

- [1] IEA. World energy outlook 2023. Tech. Rep., Paris, France: IEA; 2023, ISBN 978-92-64-35509-8 <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2023> [Accessed: 20 February 2025].
- [2] IRENA. Innovation outlook: Thermal energy storage. Tech. Rep., Abu Dhabi, UAE: International Renewable Energy Agency; 2020, <https://www.irena.org/publications/2020/Sep/Innovation-Outlook-Thermal-Energy-Storage> [Accessed: 7 February 2025].
- [3] Thiel GP, Stark AK. To decarbonize industry, we must decarbonize heat. *Joule* 2021;5(3):531–50. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2020.12.007>.
- [4] IEA. Renewables 2019: Analysis and forecast to 2024. Tech. rep., Paris, France: IEA; 2019, <https://www.iea.org/reports/renewables-2019> [Accessed 5 March 2025].
- [5] Naegler T, Simon S, Klein M, Gils HC. Quantification of the European industrial heat demand by branch and temperature level. *Int J Energy Res* 2015;39(15):2019–30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/er.3436>.
- [6] Rissman J, Bataille C, Masanet E, Aden N, Morrow WR, Zhou N, Elliott N, Dell R, Heeren N, Huckestein B, Cresko J, Miller SA, Roy J, Fennell P, Cremmins B, Koch Blank T, Hone D, Williams ED, de la Rue du Can S, Sisson B, Williams M, Katzenberger J, Burtraw D, Sethi G, Ping H, Danielson D, Lu H, Lorber T, Dinkel J, Helseth J. Technologies and policies to decarbonize global industry: Review and assessment of mitigation drivers through 2070. *Appl Energy* 2020;266:114848. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.114848>.
- [7] Madeddu S, Ueckerdt F, Pehl M, Peterseim J, Lord M, Kumar KA, Krüger C, Luderer G. The CO₂ reduction potential for the European industry via direct electrification of heat supply (power-to-heat). *Environ Res Lett* 2020;15(12):124004. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abb02>.
- [8] Beck A, Sevault A, Drexler-Schmid G, Schöny M, Kauko H. Optimal selection of thermal energy storage technology for fossil-free steam production in the processing industry. *Appl Sci* 2021;11(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/app11031063>.
- [9] Maruf MNI, Morales-España G, Sijm J, Helistö N, Kiviluoma J. Classification, potential role, and modeling of power-to-heat and thermal energy storage in energy systems: A review. *Sustain Energy Technol Assessments* 2022;53:102553. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102553>.
- [10] Khan MI, Asfand F, Al-Ghamdi SG. Progress in research and technological advancements of thermal energy storage systems for concentrated solar power. *J Energy Storage* 2022;55:105860. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2022.105860>.
- [11] Pantaleo AM, Trevisan S, Matteucci F, Cabeza LF. Innovation trends on high-temperature thermal energy storage to defossilize energy systems. *J Energy Storage* 2024;103:114261. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.114261>.
- [12] Furszyfer Del Rio DD, Sovacool BK, Griffiths S, Bazilian M, Kim J, Foley AM, Rooney D. Decarbonizing the pulp and paper industry: A critical and systematic review of sociotechnical developments and policy options. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;167:112706. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112706>.
- [13] Faraldo F, Byrne P. A review of energy-efficient technologies and decarbonating solutions for process heat in the food industry. *Energies* 2024;17(12):3051. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en17123051>.
- [14] Klooy Y, Nilsson L, Palm E. Reaching net-zero in the chemical industry—A study of roadmaps for industrial decarbonisation. *Renew Sustain Energy Transit* 2024;5:100075. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100075>.
- [15] Nurdiawati A, Urban F. Towards deep decarbonisation of energy-intensive industries: A review of current status, technologies and policies. *Energies* 2021;14(9):2408. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en14092408>.
- [16] Furszyfer Del Rio DD, Sovacool BK, Foley AM, Griffiths S, Bazilian M, Kim J, Rooney D. Decarbonizing the glass industry: A critical and systematic review of developments, sociotechnical systems and policy options. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2022;155:111885. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111885>.
- [17] Serrano-Arévalo TI, Ochoa-Barragán R, Ramírez-Márquez C, El-Halwagi M, Abdel Jabbar N, Ponce-Ortega JM. Energy storage: From fundamental principles to industrial applications. *Processes* 2025;13(6). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/pr13061853>.
- [18] Trevisan S, Pathi S, Brown J, Buchbjerg B, Borrero AB, Guedez R. Thermal performance and dynamic response assessment of an industrial molten salts based power-to-heat system. *Energy Convers Manage* 2025;342:120131. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2025.120131>.
- [19] Fambri G, Mazza A, Guelpa E, Verda V, Badami M. Power-to-heat plants in district heating and electricity distribution systems: A techno-economic analysis. *Energy Convers Manage* 2023;276:116543. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.116543>.
- [20] Kirkerud JG, Bolkesjø TF, Trømborg E. Power-to-heat as a flexibility measure for integration of renewable energy. *Energy* 2017;128:776–84. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.153>.
- [21] Bashir AA, Lund A, Pourakbari-Kasmaei M, Lehtonen M. Optimizing power and heat sector coupling for the implementation of carbon-free communities. *Energies* 2021;14(7). <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/en14071911>.
- [22] Mahmoudinezhad S, Mandø M, Arabkoohsar A. Design and techno-economic analysis of a molten-salt driven energy conversion system for sustainable process heat supply. *Renew Energy* 2023;219:119510. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119510>.
- [23] Hamilton WT, Neises TW. Dispatch optimization of electric thermal energy storage within system advisor model. *J Energy Storage* 2023;61:106786. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.106786>.
- [24] Trevisan S, Buchbjerg B, Guedez R. Power-to-heat for the industrial sector: Techno-economic assessment of a molten salt-based solution. *Energy Convers Manage* 2022;272:116362. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.116362>.
- [25] Javanshir N, Syri S, Tervo S, Rosin A. Operation of district heat network in electricity and balancing markets with the power-to-heat sector coupling. *Energy* 2023;266:126423. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.126423>.
- [26] Sihvonen V, Ollila I, Jaanto J, Grönman A, Honkapuro S, Riikonen J, Price A. Role of power-to-heat and thermal energy storage in decarbonization of district heating. *Energy* 2024;305:132372. [doi:10.1016/j.energy.2024.132372](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.132372).
- [27] González-Roubaud E, Pérez-Osorio D, Prieto C. Review of commercial thermal energy storage in concentrated solar power plants: Steam vs. molten salts. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2017;80:133–48. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.084>.
- [28] Tagle-Salazar PD, Prieto C, López-Román A, Cabeza LF. A transient heat losses model for two-tank storage systems with molten salts. *Renew Energy* 2023;219:119371. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2023.119371>.
- [29] Zaversky F, García-Barberena J, Sánchez M, Astrain D. Transient molten salt two-tank thermal storage modeling for CSP performance simulations. *Sol Energy* 2013;93:294–311. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2013.02.034>.

- [30] Pan CA, Ferruzza D, Guédez R, Dinter F, Laumert B, Haglind F. Identification of optimum molten salts for use as heat transfer fluids in parabolic trough CSP plants. a techno-economic comparative optimization. In: AIP conference proceedings. 2033, (1):2018, 030012. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.5067028>.
- [31] USDepartment of Energy (DOE). 2022 grid energy storage technology cost and performance assessment. Tech. rep., Washington, DC, USA: U.S. Department of Energy (DOE); 2022, <https://www.energy.gov/eere/analysis/2022-grid-energy-storage-technology-cost-and-performance-assessment> [Accessed 8 March 2025].
- [32] OTE a. Roční zpráva trhu s elektřinou a plynem – yearly market report. 2024, [Accessed 06 March 2026] <https://www.ote-cr.cz/cs/statistika/rocnizprava?date=2024-01-01>.
- [33] Bundesnetzagentur | SMARDde. SMARD market data download center. 2026, [Accessed 06 March 2026] <https://www.smard.de/home/downloadcenter/download-marktdaten/>.
- [34] European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E). ENTSO-e transparency platform. 2026, [Accessed 06 March 2026] <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>.
- [35] 50Hertz Transmission GmbH and Amprion GmbH and TenneT TSO GmbH and TransnetBW GmbH. Regelleistung data center: Balancing capacity and balancing energy tender results. 2026, [Accessed 06 March 2026] <https://www.regelleistung.net/apps/datacenter/tenders/>.
- [36] Ministerstvo průmyslu a obchodu ČR. Hodnota emisního faktoru CO₂ z výroby a spotřeby elektřiny. 2025, [Accessed 06 March 2026] <https://www.mpo.gov.cz/cz/energetika/statistika/elektrina-a-teplo/hodnota-emisniho-faktoru-co2-z-vyroby-a-spotreby-elektřiny-286666/>.
- [37] ČEPS a. CEPS data – electricity generation and system information. 2026, [Accessed 06 March 2026] <https://www.ceps.cz/cs/data#Generation>.
- [38] Electricity Maps. Live electricity data for Germany (15 minute interval). 2026, [Accessed 06 March 2026] https://app.electricitymaps.com/map/zone/DE/live/fifteen_minutes.
- [39] Steinmann W-D, Eck M. Buffer storage for direct steam generation. Sol Energy 2006;80(10):1277–82. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2005.05.013>, Solar Power and Chemical Energy Systems (SolarPACES'04).
- [40] European Parliament and Council of the European Union. Directive (EU) 2023/959 of the European parliament and of the council of 10 may 2023 amending directive 2003/87/EC establishing a system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the union. 2023, [Accessed 24 April 2026] <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/959/oj>.
- [41] Azevedo P. Thermal properties. Technical Report LEN-UER-2018-N07-IR, Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia (LNEG); 2018, <https://repositorio.lneg.pt/entities/publication/b0cf415a-56aa-407b-9e2b-c0ea309a6c6a> [Accessed 8 March 2025].
- [42] Energetický regulační úřad. Cenové rozhodnutí č. 11/2024 ze dne 29. listopadu 2024. 2024, <https://eru.gov.cz/sites/default/files/obsah/prilohy/erv132024.pdf> Energetický regulační věstník, částka 13/2024.
- [43] EDIS Netz GmbH. Preisblatt netzentgelte strom. 2024, https://www.e-dis-netz.de/content/dam/revu-global/e-dis-netz/dokumente/Preisblaetter_Netzentgelte_Strom_20240101.pdf.
- [44] Große R, CHRISTOPHER B, STEFAN W, Geyer R, Robbi S, et al. Long term (2050) projections of techno-economic performance of large-scale heating and cooling in the EU. Tech. rep., EUR28859, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union; 2017, <http://dx.doi.org/10.2760/24422>, JRC109006.
- [45] Zhang Q, Yi H, Yu Z, Gao J, Wang X, Lin H, Shen B. Energy-exergy analysis and energy efficiency improvement of coal-fired industrial boilers based on thermal test data. Appl Therm Eng 2018;144:614–27. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.08.069>.
- [46] Juhrich K. CO₂ Emission factors for fossil fuels: Update 2022. Tech. rep., German Environment Agency (UBA); 2022, https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/system/files/medien/479/publikationen/cc_29-2022_emission-factors-fossil-fuels.pdf.
- [47] ČEPS. Metodika pro hodnocení zdrojové přiměřenosti. Tech. rep., ČEPS, a.s.; 2024, <https://www.ceps.cz/cs/zdrojova-primerenost>.